

Pest resistance—diseases

Impact of seedborne bacteria on rice seedlings

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We studied the bacterial populations in seeds of different rice cultivars and evaluated their effect on seed germination and seedling vigor.

We used serial dilution technique to examine seeds of rice cultivars Jaya, Gowrisanna, Rajamudi, Shakti, and Rajakayame for externally borne (from surface wash) and internally borne (from crushed seeds) bacterial populations. Colonies morphologically different in dilution plates were transferred separately to nutrient agar slants and Gram-stained.

The effect of bacteria on seed quality was assessed using cultures grown in nutrient broth for 24 h at 25 ± 2°C. Surface-sterilized seeds were soaked in the bacterial cultures for 24 h. Treated seeds were tested for germination using the paper towel method. Controls were seeds soaked in uninoculated medium and in sterile water. Sprouts were counted daily for 5 d. Root and shoot lengths were measured on the 5th or 14th days and a seedling vigor index calculated. Patho-

genicity of each bacterial isolate was tested by the cut-and-inoculate method.

Seeds of all five cultivars carried bacteria. Internal bacteria outnumbered external bacteria (Table 1). Most bacteria were Gram-negative and varied in size from coccus bacilli to long filamentous forms. Only one Gram-positive strain was isolated from Shakti; it was internally seedborne.

Table 1. Bacteria borne externally and internally by rice seed, Mysore, India.

Cultivar	Externally borne bacteria (10 ² cells/g of seed)	Internally borne bacteria (10 ³ cells/g of seed)
Jaya	10.0	31.0
Gowrisanna	50.0	267.0
Rajamudi	10.6	26.0
Shakti	8.5	3.0
Rajakayame	11.0	5.0

Sprouted rice seed showed differential responses to the presence of bacterial cultures. The response differed not only between bacteria, but also in terms of germination, root growth, shoot growth, and vigor. The stimulatory or inhibitory effects of bacteria toward allied hosts followed no particular pattern (Table 2). Vigor increased in Gowrisanna and decreased in Jaya, Rajamudi, and Shakti. Rajakayame seedlings showed both stimulatory and inhibitory effects.

Most of the cultures that reduced vigor were capable of producing symptoms when inoculated to rice seedlings. Symptoms included dry appearance, curly blades, and yellow leaves. Bacterial infection in general produced varied effects.

Of 18 isolates tested, only two interacted with Shakti; 15 interacted with Gowrisanna (Table 2). The vigor of Gowrisanna seedlings suggests that the bacterial colonization of its seeds may be beneficial. □

Table 2. Cross interaction of bacterial isolates. ^a Mysore, India.

Culture ^b isolated from cultivar	Cultures tested (no.)	Jaya		Gowrisanna		Rajamudi		Shakti		Rajakayame	
		IC (no.)	VI	IC (no.)	VI	IC (no.)	VI	IC (no.)	VI	IC (no.)	VI
Gs	6	3	*	4	+	3	-	1	-	2	*
Sh	5	4	-	4	+	4	-	Nil	*	-	+
Rm	3	2	-	3	+	2	-	1	-	Nil	*
Rk	2	1	-	2	+	2	-	Nil	*	Nil	*
Jaya	2	1	-	2	+	2	-	Nil	*	1	-

^a VI = Vigorindex: - = inhibition, + = stimulation, * = no effect compared to control. IC = Cultures causing interaction.

^b Gs = Gowrisanna, Sh = Shakti, Rm = Rajamudi, Rk = Rajakayame.

Identifying tolerance for rice tungro (RTV)-associated viruses in rice varieties using severity index scoring and serology

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We used the new scoring method to evaluate 15 selected varieties for resistance to or tolerance for RTV.

Each variety was seeded at 20 seeds/pot, with three replications. At 10 d after seeding, one pot/variety was batch-inoculated for 3 h in a cage containing 10 viruliferous GLH/seedling. (GLH had fed on plants infected with rice tungro bacilliform [RTBV] and rice tungro spherical [RTSV] viruses for 4 d.)

Seedlings were scored individually 4 wk after inoculation. Leaf samples were also collected and indexed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay

(ELISA) for the presence of RTV-associated viruses.

Based on their severity index (score 1-3 = resistant, 4-6 = intermediate, and 7-9 = susceptible), Utri Rajapan (Acc. 16684), ARC11554, Pankhari 203, Balimau Putih, Utri Merah (Acc. 16680), and Tilockkachari can be considered resistant (see table).

Based on ELISA, only ARC11554 and Utri Merah had less than 10% infection by RTV-associated viruses. Utri Rajapan, Pankhari 203, Balimau

Putih, and Tilockkachari had high infection by either RTBV alone or RTBV + RTSV.

The very low symptoms on these varieties (average score 2.5), despite high infection by RTV-associated viruses, indicate tolerance for tungro. The varieties exhibited less than 10% reduction in plant height and no leaf discoloration, despite infection by either RTBV alone or RTBV + RTSV.

Other varieties that had intermediate to susceptible reactions had high infection. Susceptible check TN1 had an average severity index score of 8.9 and 98.3% infection by RTBV + RTSV combined.

These results indicate the importance of scoring RTV infection not only on the basis of symptoms, but also through serology. □

Reaction of selected varieties to rice tungro-associated viruses, using the improved mass screening method and ELISA. IRRI, 1989.

Variety	Acc. no.	Average severity index ^a	Plants (%) infected with		
			RTBV	RTSV	RTBV + RTSV
TN1	-	8.9	1.7	0.0	98.3
Utri Rajapan	16684	2.9	45.0	3.7	32.7
ARC11554	21473	1.9	10.0	0.0	0.0
Pankhari 203	5999	2.7	76.0	1.7	0.0
ASD7	6303	5.7	44.7	0.0	6.7
Balimau Putih	17204	2.1	0.0	19.3	61.7
ASD8	6393	6.1	44.7	0.0	6.3
TKM6	237	5.9	89.7	0.0	0.0
Utri Merah	16680	2.5	6.0	0.0	0.0
Jhingasail	8336	6.2	19.3	2.0	78.7
Goria	26345	4.7	63.3	0.0	28.3
Choron Bawla	26323	4.4	45.0	0.0	49.3
Tilockkachari	8321	2.3	21.7	1.7	3.3
Kashiabinni	37488	4.2	50.3	1.7	1.7
Palasithari 601	12069	4.9	83.7	0.0	0.0

^a Scale and descriptions: 1 = no symptoms, 3 = 1-10% plant height reduction with no leaf discoloration, 5 = 11-30% plant height reduction with no distinct leaf discoloration, 7 = 31-50% plant height reduction and/or yellow to orange leaf discoloration, 9 = more than 50% plant height reduction and yellow to orange leaf discoloration.

Production of helper component in rice tungro virus (RTSV)-infected plants

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Rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) are transmitted by the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. RTBV can be acquired and transmitted only by GLH that have fed on RTSV-source plants. RTSV particles do not bear the helper function for RTBV transmission, but a hypothetical helper compo-

nent is produced in RTSV-infected plants.

We exposed 7-d-old TN1 seedlings transplanted in pots separately to four or five RTSV-viruliferous GLH for 12-h inoculation feeding. At 0, 12, 24, 36, 48, 60, 72, 84, 96, and 108 h after RTSV inoculation, a seedling was confined in a cage with a batch of virus-free GLH adults for 12 h. Then, the batch of GLH was given 10-12 h inoculation feeding on TN1 plants infected with RTBV alone. After that acquisition feeding, individual GLH were given a 1-d inoculation feeding on a 7-d-old TN1 seedling in a test tube.

One month after inoculation, seedlings were indexed by ELISA for the presence of RTBV and RTSV.

GLH that fed on RTSV-inoculated plants 36 h and longer after inoculation transmitted RTBV (see table). GLH that fed on RTSV-source plants at 72 h and longer after inoculation, then on RTBV-source plants, were infective for both RTBV and RTBV + RTSV.

These results indicate that RTSV-infected plants began to serve as a source for the helper component 36 h after inoculation and as a source for tungro 72 h after inoculation. □

Transmission of RTBV and RTSV to TN1 seedlings after a 1-d feeding by GLH that had fed 12 h on RTSV source plants 0 to 108 h after a 12-h inoculation feeding by RTSV-viruliferous GLH and then for 12 h on RTBV source plants IRRI, 1989.

Feeding sequence			GLH (no.) tested	GLH (no.) that transmitted		
1st (12 h) ^a	2d (12 h)	Inoculation (24 h)		RTBV	RTBV+ RTSV	RTSV
RTSV (12)	RTBV	TN1	35	0	0	0
RTSV (24)	RTBV	TN1	32	0	0	0
RTSV (36)	RTBV	TN1	44	3	0	0
RTSV (48)	RTBV	TN1	37	3	2	0
RTSV (60)	RTBV	TN1	23	2	0	0
RTSV (72)	RTBV	TN1	25	3	3	0
RTSV (84)	RTBV	TN1	32	4	3	0
RTSV (96)	RTBV	TN1	30	6	6	1
RTSV (108)	RTBV	TN1	27	5	3	3

^a Number in parentheses indicates hours after inoculation with RTSV.

Effect of vector resistance on tungro (RTV) transmission

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Predominant rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) transmission by RTV-viruliferous green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* has been observed in GLH-resistant IR varieties. We examined this contradiction using GLH-resistant and susceptible cultivars.

ARC11554, IR5492, IR74, and IR36 were given six sequential 4-h inocula-